

Creative Solutions and Applications of Sheep Wool

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Wool yarn and spindle

In the Terra Fria Transmontana region, wool from sheep of the indigenous breeds Churra Galega Bragançana Preta ou Branca and Churra Galega Mirandesa has traditionally been used to make clothing and household utilities (e.g. jumpers, socks, bedspreads, rugs), as well as articles to support agricultural activities (e.g. grain sacks and saddlebags). Compared to other breeds, they don't have fibres with the fineness required by the textile industry, but given their characteristics, such as their greater thickness and length, they can be used for different purposes. The commercial use of wool in Portugal has decreased over the last few years and is subject to continuous devaluation. Shearing, which is necessary for thermal comfort and animal hygiene, is often seen as a financial burden for the producer and the wool as waste that is difficult to dispose of. It is important to emphasise that, due to its characteristics, wool has shown great potential and diverse possibilities for use as a thermal and acoustic insulation material and as a fire retardant. Its use stands out in the construction industry (for example, in internal walls) and textiles (such as in firefighters' uniforms and hypoallergenic duvets), as well as being used to upholster furniture, reinforce bricks, insulate packaging and as an absorbent material, particularly to contain oil spillages. It has also been widely used in craft initiatives and projects and in various artistic dimensions. This natural product can be also used as a ground cover in gardens or vegetable plots (mulching), favoring weeding by reducing the growth of unwanted plants, controlling the temperature and retaining moisture in the soil. In addition, during decomposition, the wool enriches the soil with organic matter, improving its fertility. The use of wool is a natural and biodegradable alternative to both synthetic fibres and other chemical compounds, and its sustainable production contributes to the important decarbonisation of the economy.

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